

Spatial variations in colorectal cancer mortality in England and Wales

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Summary

Colorectal cancer is an important public health issue in the UK, accounting for over 16,000 deaths each year. This study used death registration data to examine trends in colorectal cancer mortality by geographic location and socio-economic deprivation over a 20-year period in England and Wales. Mortality rates declined rapidly over the study period with the lowest rates observed among the least deprived group, particularly for men. The spatial pattern in colorectal cancer mortality was not as clear as that for all-cancers combined, however, some clusters of high and low colorectal cancer mortality were identified.

KEYWORDS: health geography, mortality, deprivation, colorectal cancer

1. Introduction

Colorectal cancer (CRC) is the fourth most common cancer in the UK and second most common cause of cancer death. Over 42,000 cases are diagnosed annually, leading to over 16,000 deaths (Cancer Research UK, 2021). While there has been a considerable decrease in CRC mortality rates over recent decades it remains a major public health concern.

Reducing socio-economic and geographic inequalities in cancer outcomes has been a key policy aim since publication of the NHS Cancer Plan (Department of Health, 2000) but disparities have persisted. There is extensive literature relating to differences in CRC incidence, survival and mortality by socio-economic deprivation (Aarts et al. 2010). A report by the National Cancer Intelligence Network (2014) found evidence of an association between CRC mortality and socio-economic deprivation in England.

Geographical variations in CRC morbidity and mortality are less well described. While evidence of inequalities in incidence and survival have been reported at region level in England (Walters et al. 2011, Arik et al. 2020), this study investigated variation at a more local level. Trends in CRC mortality in England and Wales over the period 1990 to 2012 were examined, by geographic location and socio-economic deprivation at Local Authority (LA) level. These trends were compared to those for all-cancers combined. Examining mortality at sub-regional level is important to understand the impact of local characteristics on the risk of cancer death and to target interventions to reduce geographic variation.

2. Data

Death registration data for England and Wales was sourced from the UK Data Service (UKDS) for the period 1990 to 2012 at LA level. The data set contained the annual number of deaths in each LA for

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which CRC was recorded as the underlying cause of death, split by sex and five-year age group. CRC was defined according to the World Health Organisation (WHO) International Classification of Diseases, version 9 and 10. For deaths prior to 2001, CRC was classified by ICD-9 codes 153 and 154 and from 1 January 2001, ICD-10 codes C18-21. The 2011 LA geographies were used in the analysis, of which there were 348 in England and Wales. There was no corresponding mortality data for two LAs, City of London and Isles of Scilly, which were removed from the analysis, leaving a total of 346 LAs. Annual mortality data for the same time period was obtained for all neoplasms at LA level, split by sex and five year age-group, to enable comparisons to be made with CRC mortality trends.

Annual mid-year population estimates by LA, sex and five-year age group were sourced from the Office for National Statistics (ONS) for the period 1990 to 2012. Mid-year population estimates relate to the usually resident population on 30 June of each year.

The Townsend Deprivation Index is a census-based index of material deprivation derived from a combination of four census variables: person's unemployed, overcrowded households, households without a car and households not owner-occupied. Townsend scores were calculated for each LA using data at each census time point (1991, 2001 and 2011). In the analysis presented here, Townsend scores based on 2001 data have been used as this represents the mid-point of the study period. In order to compare mortality trends by area type, the index scores were categorised into (population weighted) quintiles: 1 being the least deprived and 5 the most deprived. LA digital boundary data was sourced from the ONS (Office for National Statistics, 2019).

3. Methods

To investigate trends by area type, the mortality and population data were aggregated across Townsend deprivation quintiles. Directly-standardised mortality rates were calculated for each year within the study period based on a 3-year rolling average (in order to remove any yearly fluctuations in mortality rates). In the geographical analysis, directly-standardised mortality rates were calculated by LA using 3-years of data pooled around each census year (results for 2011 are presented here). Data was pooled due to small numbers of deaths when split by LA.

Standardisation methods were used in order to account for differences in age structure between the populations of geographical areas. This is particularly necessary in this context as CRC mortality is strongly related to age. Directly standardised rates and confidence intervals were estimated by applying the observed age-specific mortality rates in the study population to the age distribution of a given standard population. The 2013 European Standard Population (ESP) was used in this analysis.

The Getis-Ord G_i^* statistic was computed to identify whether there were statistically significant clusters of high and low CRC mortality rates at LA level. The neighbourhood around each LA was defined based on areas that share a boundary.

4. Results

There were 341,234 CRC deaths in England and Wales between 1990 and 2012. CRC mortality rates declined rapidly over the study period across all deprivation quintiles (**Figure 1**). The lowest mortality rates were observed among the least deprived group throughout the study period, however there was no consistent difference in the mortality rates of the other four groups. By the end of the time period the mortality rates among these four groups had converged and were significantly higher than that in the least deprived group.

Figure 1 CRC mortality by deprivation, England and Wales, 1990-2012

Consistently higher CRC mortality rates were observed for males compared to females which is in line with trends in the UK and globally. Among men, the lowest mortality rates were found in the least deprived quintile, followed by the second least deprived quintile, however, there was little variation in female mortality rates by deprivation (**Figure 2**). In comparison, there was a clear deprivation gradient in all-cancer mortality over the same time period (**Figure 3**).

Figure 2 CRC mortality by sex and deprivation, England and Wales, 1990-2012

Figure 3 All-cancer mortality by deprivation, England and Wales, 1990-2012

CRC mortality rates ranged from 14 deaths per 100,000 (Rugby) to 52 deaths per 100,000 (Eden). The higher mortality rates were generally found in coastal and peripheral areas (**Figure 4**). In comparison, there were high rates of all-cause mortality in the north of England and Wales and low rates in the south-east of England (**Figure 5**) which could reflect the stronger socio-economic gradient in all-cancer mortality rates.

Figure 4 CRC mortality by LA, England and Wales, 2011

Figure 5 All-cancer mortality by LA, England and Wales, 2011

The spatial variability in CRC mortality was quantified using the Getis-Ord G_i^* statistic. Statistically significant hot spots of high CRC mortality were found in south Wales, Lincolnshire and Cumbria. Conversely, statistically significant cold spots of low CRC mortality rates were found in the south east of England, north-west London and in the West Midlands (**Figure 6**).

Figure 6 CRC mortality hot and cold spots, England and Wales, 2011

A time-series of CRC mortality rates by population density category, used as a proxy for rurality, shows the lowest rates were consistently found in the most densely-populated areas (**Figure 7**) but there was not a clear gradient by density category. There may be other factors besides socio-economic deprivation and rurality that could explain the geographic variation in mortality rates. Furthermore, LA may be too coarse a geography to identify clear spatial patterns.

Figure 7 CRC mortality by population density, England and Wales, 1990-2012

5. Further work

An application to access individual death registration data for England and Wales up to 2018 has been submitted to the UK Data Service and is pending approval. Access to individual-level data is required as small counts are suppressed in the openly published mortality data which led to problems when calculating directly-standardised rates.

A time-series of mortality rates based on trajectories of area deprivation rather than a cross-section will also be examined. This will allow mortality trends in areas with persistently high or low, or improving/worsening deprivation over the study period to be compared.

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Biographies

Charlotte Sturley is a postgraduate researcher based in the Leeds Institute for Data Analytics. Her PhD investigates social and spatial variations in colorectal cancer in England and Wales. She has a BA in Geography and an MSc in Geographical Information Systems along with five years industry experience as a retail analyst.

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